

3D Model Representations of Crosses with Micro-Relief Utilizing Photogrammetry and NeRFs Techniques

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Abstract

This paper investigates the creation of three-dimensional (3D) digital representations of miniature crosses featuring micro-reliefs, utilizing photogrammetry and Neural Radiance Fields (NeRFs). The primary objective is to develop high-quality 3D models using accessible software and low-cost equipment, thereby facilitating broader applications in cultural heritage documentation. We focus on NeRFs because they offer a comparable approach to 3D reconstruction by learning from image sequences or videos, producing high-quality results efficiently.

This research compares two methods for capturing miniature religious crosses composed of complex materials such as metal, wood, and semiprecious stones. Due to their sensitive nature, intricate structure, and reflective surfaces, these objects present significant challenges for accurate 3D capture. We emphasize how NeRFs can address some limitations of photogrammetry by better managing complex lighting and producing detailed reconstructions, even in the presence of challenging artifacts. The results indicate that photogrammetry ensures geometric precision, while NeRFs enhances visual and material interpretation. Although NeRFs technology has not yet achieved the accuracy of advanced photogrammetric setups, its speed, simplicity, and low hardware requirements make it a promising alternative for cultural heritage documentation. This research highlights NeRFs potential as a future tool for enabling both remote study and digital preservation of small-scale artifacts. This contribution is positioned as a pilot comparative study using a structured, anchored ordinal scoring scheme to capture expert-perceived differences in representational fidelity, particularly for reflective micro-relief surfaces. The analysis is therefore reported as comparative observations rather than benchmark-grade quantitative performance claims.

Keywords: 3D models, NeRFs, Blessing cross, Sanctification cross, digital modeling, photogrammetry, digital modeling problems.

Introduction

In the field of conservation and three-dimensional preservation of cultural heritage, many materials present significant challenges due to their resource-intensive and time-consuming nature. Among the most complex are materials with highly reflective or translucent surfaces, such as gold, silver, bronze, glass, coral, pearls, and other reflective metals and precious or semi-precious stones. Historically, producing a coherent model required thorough documentation, as well as substantial time and financial investment. However, recent advances in computer graphics have introduced powerful tools for three-dimensional (3D) digitisation and modeling of artworks, including those with small dimensions and intricate relief details. Contemporary 3D techniques in computer graphics can be employed to reconstruct and visualize objects with complex material appearances. A primary challenge in 3D digitization remains how to create accurate replicas of miniature art objects using accessible software without relying on expensive hardware. In this work, we address the challenges encountered when creating 3D model representations of crosses with micro-relief using photogrammetry and NeRFs-based techniques (Mildenhall, et al. 2020; Martin-Brualla, et al. 2021). NeRFs offer capabilities that traditional methods cannot provide, introducing novel approaches to view synthesis and effectively handling reflective and complex surfaces. Our goal is to evaluate the usefulness of NeRFs as a tool for conservators, particularly for small and intricate blessing and sanctification crosses made from various materials with differing reflective properties. This study concludes that, while photogrammetry remains a precise tool for small-scale modeling, NeRFs is faster, more accessible, and, in some demanding cases, can produce more visually accurate digital documentation of cultural heritage. This contribution is presented as a pilot study that uses a structured qualitative assessment protocol to compare photogrammetry and NeRF-based neural rendering for small-scale, reflective cultural heritage objects. It does not claim benchmark-grade metric validation; instead, it aims to clarify when and why representational fidelity (e.g. view-dependent reflectance, perceived materiality) may be operationally valuable for conservation study and communication.

Research Questions

RQ1: Under a low-cost capture setup, how do photogrammetry and NeRF differ in the perceived legibility of micro-relief and reflective material appearance for miniature crosses?

RQ2: Which object features (e.g., polished metal, glass insets, wire ornament) systematically trigger failure modes in each method?

RQ3: What is the practical trade-off between metric reliability (geometry) and representational fidelity (view-dependent appearance) for conservation-oriented use cases?

Neural Radiance Fields (NeRFs) Approaches in Cultural Heritage Digitisation

The advent of Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques, specifically Neural Rendering (NR) methods such as NeRFs and 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS) (Kerbl et al., 2023), represents a paradigm shift in the digital documentation and study of cultural heritage (CH) objects and monuments (Balloni et al., 2024; Sambugaro et al., 2024). This review examines

recent approaches utilizing NeRFs in CH contexts, drawing on methodologies and findings presented in contemporary literature. Numerous contemporary approaches investigate the potential of NeRFs primarily through comparative analyses with established photogrammetric methods— Structure-from-Motion and Multi-View Stereo (SfM/MVS)—and occasionally with Terrestrial Laser Scanning (TLS). These studies often focus on scenarios that are traditionally challenging for conventional techniques (Remondino et al., 2023; Balloni et al., 2023; Balloni et al., 2024; Zainuddin et al., 2024).

Several studies have established rigorous comparative pipelines to evaluate NeRF performance. These generally involve acquiring a dataset of multi-view images, deriving accurate camera poses—often using conventional photogrammetry software such as COLMAP or Agisoft Metashape—and then training the respective NR model, i.e., NeRF or 3DGS (Remondino et al., 2023; Murtiyoso et al., 2023a; Croce et al., 2024; Sambugaro et al., 2024; Zainuddin et al., 2024). A critical first step is identifying the optimal NeRF implementations for cultural heritage (CH) applications. Studies comparing multiple state-of-the-art methods found that Instant-NGP (noted for its speed; Müller et al., 2022) and Nerfacto (valued for its balance of speed and quality) consistently outperformed alternatives across diverse datasets (Remondino et al., 2023; Balloni et al., 2024).

Quantitative metrics are crucial for objective evaluation. Approaches have utilized terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) or high-resolution photogrammetry as ground truth (GT) references (Balloni et al., 2023; Mazzacca et al., 2023; Zainuddin et al., 2024). The core metric often used is the deviation between reconstructed point clouds—derived from NeRF’s volumetric representation via techniques such as marching cubes or Poisson reconstruction—and the reference data. This deviation is measured using indicators such as Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Standard Deviation (STD) through cloud-to-cloud comparison (Remondino et al., 2023; Murtiyoso et al., 2023a; Zainuddin et al., 2024).

Beyond simple distance comparisons, methodologies have employed specialized analyses, including surface deviation and noise level assessment (Remondino et al., 2023), volumetric rendering quality evaluation using Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR), Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM), and Learned Perceptual Image Patch Similarity (LPIPS) (Balloni et al., 2024; Arshad et al., 2024), and structural analyses such as F-score (precision and recall) to quantify completeness and accuracy (Arshad et al., 2024).

A primary motivation for applying NeRF is its superior ability to handle complex surface properties where traditional photometric consistency often fails (Remondino et al., 2023; Mazzacca et al., 2023; Balloni et al., 2024). Non-collaborative surfaces: NeRF methods have demonstrated superior performance over photogrammetry for objects featuring textureless, metallic, translucent, refractive, or highly reflective surfaces (Croce et al., 2024; Mazzacca et al., 2023). Specific case studies highlight NeRF’s capacity to render view-dependent variations, such as reflections on a bronze lectern or stucco decorations, resulting in significantly more realistic visual outputs compared to the flat, matte textures produced by photogrammetry (Croce et al., 2023, Croce et al., 2024). In interior mapping, NeRF uniquely generated points on challenging elements like glass windows, where multi-view stereo (MVS) solutions completely failed (Murtiyoso et al., 2023b). Similarly, NeRF successfully reconstructed portions of a transparent pedestal on a bronze statue (Mazzacca et al., 2023). Scene completeness and data scarcity: NeRF excels at filling

gaps in reconstruction caused by limited input data, occlusions, or suboptimal camera views (Balloni et al., 2023; Croce et al., 2023; Croce et al., 2024a). NeRF models achieved greater completeness than photogrammetric models in datasets with limited visual data—for instance, reconstructing less visible regions of a statue, elements behind a stove in a niche, or components of a facade partially obscured or poorly lit (Balloni et al., 2023; Croce et al., 2024a). The NeRF method proved valuable when dealing with historical image archives or low-quality, unconstrained tourist photos (Photo-tourism / NeRF-W), enabling reconstruction even when traditional photogrammetry struggled with large baselines or inconsistencies (Mazzacca et al., 2023; Croce et al., 2023).

Recent literature has introduced comparisons among the latest neural rendering (NR) paradigms. NeRF (Nerfacto) (Tancik et al., 2023) is recognized for its high speed and quality visual rendering, making it ideal for rapid scene exploration (Balloni et al., 2024). However, it generally produces limited mesh detail, often resulting in coarse representations with clusters, jagged surfaces, or artifacts in flat areas (Balloni et al., 2024; Sambugaro et al., 2024). The Signed Distance Function (SDF) approach, also known as Bakedangelo, is distinguished for generating high-fidelity meshes with precise details (Balloni et al., 2024). This method is well-suited for applications requiring detailed reconstruction, such as monument degradation studies, but suffers from significantly longer computation times—up to 24 hours for complete training (Balloni et al., 2024). 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS or SuGaR) offers a versatile compromise, providing moderate computation speed (approximately 1 hour of training) and good mesh quality, making it applicable to a wide range of scenarios (Balloni et al., 2024). 3DGS has been highlighted for its superior detail and accurate capture of complex structures due to precise normal calculations, suggesting it could become a future replacement for traditional mesh representations (Balloni et al., 2024; Sambugaro et al., 2024).

The application of NeRF in the Cultural Heritage (CH) domain presents significant ethical and integration challenges. Ethical concerns include transparency, fairness, and responsibility. The use of NR, driven by AI paradigms, necessitates a robust ethical framework to address risks such as the authenticity and intellectual property of digital replicas (Stacchio et al., 2024). Key challenges involve the lack of interpretability of complex AI models (transparency), potential biases in pre-trained models (fairness), and accountability for inaccurate or distorted outputs (responsibility) (Stacchio et al., 2024). Data dependency and quality issues also arise. NeRF's reliability depends heavily on the initial image orientation. If the SfM process (e.g., COLMAP) fails, NeRF cannot produce accurate results (Balloni et al., 2023; Croce et al., 2023; Zainuddin et al., 2024). Even with accurate camera poses, NeRF reconstructions often yield point clouds that are significantly noisier and exhibit higher geometric errors than those produced by Multi-View Stereo (MVS) methods. In some rock art documentation tests, errors reached centimeter levels, making NeRF outputs unsuitable for precise metric documentation (Murtiyoso et al., 2023b; Zainuddin et al., 2024). Another challenge is the conversion bottleneck. NeRF's primary output is a volumetric radiance field optimized for view synthesis rather than an explicit geometric model (Croce et al., 2023; Murtiyoso et al., 2023b; Zainuddin et al., 2024). Converting this output into conventional representations

such as point clouds or meshes typically requires algorithms like Marching Cubes, which can introduce noise, degrade quality, and cause issues such as model fragmentation or holes (Palestini et al., 2020; Remondino et al., 2023; Croce et al., 2024; Sambugaro et al., 2024).

Based on comparative analysis and critical assessment, integrating NeRF technology into demanding CH item digitization workflows presents a unique set of strengths, limitations, advantages, and challenges.

Main strengths include the handling of non-collaborative surfaces, enhanced realism in view synthesis, and greater completeness in data-sparse scenarios. NeRFs inherently excel at capturing and rendering scenes with materials that are challenging for traditional photogrammetry, such as reflective, metallic, translucent, or homogeneous surfaces, due to the view-dependent nature of their volumetric representation (Remondino et al., 2023, Croce et al., 2023, Murtiyoso et al., 2023b, Croce et al., 2024a). The focus on view synthesis enables NeRFs to generate highly photorealistic novel views and capture view-dependent visual effects (e.g., reflections, lighting variations) with exceptional fidelity, significantly enhancing the visual experience for virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) applications (Croce et al., 2024a; Croce et al., 2024b; Fabra et al., 2024; Sambugaro et al., 2024). NeRFs demonstrate superior performance in completing models where data scarcity exists, such as in areas with occlusions, sparse image coverage, or limited viewing angles, producing more complete geometric results than corresponding photogrammetric models (Croce et al., 2023; Mazzacca et al., 2023; Croce et al., 2024a).

Main Limitations. For rigorous metric documentation required in conservation science, NeRF models exhibit significantly higher noise levels and lower geometric precision—often with errors on the order of centimeters—compared to established MVS and TLS methods, which achieve millimeter-level accuracy (Murtiyoso et al., 2023b; Croce et al., 2024a; Zainuddin et al., 2024). The reliance on post-processing steps (e.g., Marching Cubes) to convert the implicit radiance field into an explicit mesh or point cloud introduces artifacts, noise, and geometric inaccuracies, thereby limiting the quality of the resulting geometric model (Croce et al., 2023; Murtiyoso et al., 2023b; Sambugaro et al., 2024; Croce et al., 2024a). Although volumetric rendering excels, the textures extracted and applied to the derived 3D meshes often exhibit lower resolution and blurring compared to photogrammetry, which impairs the legibility of fine details, particularly at high scales of representation (e.g., 1:5) (Croce et al., 2024a; Zainuddin et al., 2024). NeRFs methods typically require initial camera poses derived from traditional SfM/COLMAP workflows; therefore, if photogrammetric orientation fails, NeRF reconstruction is generally not feasible (Balloni et al., 2023; Croce et al., 2023; Sambugaro et al., 2024).

Advantages for Cultural Heritage (CH) Workflows. NeRF implementations, particularly Instant-NGP and Nerfacto, significantly reduce processing and training times compared to traditional MVS, often cutting processing time by half or more. This enables faster reconstruction of large datasets (Mazzacca et al., 2023; Zainuddin et al., 2024; Sambugaro et al., 2024). NeRF's ability to generate detailed 3D representations from limited image sets makes it especially valuable for non-invasive documentation of fragile or inaccessible cultural heritage sites (Balloni et al., 2024). The application of NeRF-W (Photo-tourism) to unconstrained touristic or archival images provides a viable and

efficient approach for reconstructing 3D models of lost monuments, overcoming challenges faced by conventional methods when dealing with heterogeneous datasets (Mazzacca et al., 2023).

Challenges in Integration Protocols. The significant variance in NeRF output quality—ranging from high visual realism to low geometric accuracy—requires practitioners to carefully align the chosen reconstruction method with the intended scale and purpose of documentation (e.g., exploration versus precise metric analysis) (Balloni et al., 2023; Croce et al., 2024a). Although faster implementations exist, NeRF models remain computationally intensive, necessitating substantial GPU power (e.g., NVIDIA 3000 series or higher) for optimal training and rendering. This requirement may pose constraints for resource-limited institutions (Fabra et al., 2024; Sambugaro et al., 2024; Croce et al., 2024a). The integration of NeRFs technology requires the development of new guidelines to address ethical risks related to the transparency, reliability, and authenticity of generated digital twins, particularly concerning data ownership and accountability for potentially misleading reconstructions (Stacchio et al., 2024).

NeRFs technology, particularly when employing advanced methods such as Nerfacto or Instant-NGP, serves as a powerful complementary tool to photogrammetry, significantly enhancing the aesthetic quality and completeness of CH digitization, especially for challenging materials and scenes with limited data. However, it cannot currently replace conventional MVS or terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) in metric surveying workflows that require high geometric accuracy and low noise levels (Balloni et al., 2023; Mazzacca et al., 2023; Zainuddin et al., 2024). Future research aims to explore synergistic approaches that integrate the geometric accuracy of photogrammetry with the synthesis capabilities of NeRF/3DGS to achieve truly robust and high-fidelity digital documentation (Mazzacca et al., 2023; Croce et al., 2023; Croce et al., 2024a).

Accordingly, the study is framed as a low-cost, practice-oriented comparison intended to clarify (i) which object/material characteristics systematically challenge each approach and (ii) how these differences matter for conservation-oriented tasks (e.g., visual legibility of micro-relief, perceived materiality, documentation for remote study). Because no colorimetric calibration or metric ground truth is introduced, the comparative evaluation is intentionally structured qualitative, not a metrological benchmark.

Methods

This study examines the 3D digitization of religious crosses used for blessing or sanctification. The methods employed to create the 3D models include photogrammetry and NeRFs. We examine the practical application of these imaging techniques and assess their capacity to produce reliable digital representations of complex miniature artworks. Specific challenges discussed include complex material textures and varying reflective properties. NeRFs utilize neural rendering to synthesize novel views and capture intricate surface details. Video-derived image sequences can also be used in NeRF workflows, which may offer a practical option in this context. Their speed, efficiency, and low hardware requirements make them a cost-effective method for producing high-quality results. Additionally, NeRFs effectively handle reflections and color variations caused by

metallic surfaces, resulting in more realistic visualizations. Unique miniature objects, due to their construction techniques, fragile materials, and inherent vulnerability, can be challenging to access for documentation and study. The artifacts we examine include blessing crosses made from various materials such as metal, curved wood, pigments, and semiprecious stones. For this case study, we selected four different crosses (Fig. 1) to provide a general overview of the challenges associated with each technique.

Figure 1. Four crosses made from various materials: 1) A1: Metal cross with semiprecious stones, 2) A2: Metal cross with semiprecious stones and an ivory substitute center on a marble base, 3) B3: Wooden cross with pigments, 4) B4: Metal cross with a wooden core.

Group A

Group A consists of two newly crafted crosses from a private collection. These crosses are special commissions, created as mementos commemorating the return of part of the relics of Saint Kosmas the Hermit from Italy. Although they share the same theme, their construction materials differ. They were selected to conduct initial 3D tests and to observe the variability of the materials, as well as to assess how easily—or with what difficulty—they can be rendered. Unlike older crosses, these newer ones lack the patina of age and still retain their glossy surfaces. Combined with vitreous coatings and low relief, they proved to be particularly challenging cases.

1. Cross A1 is a small gold-plated cross adorned with semi-precious stones. It is made from a gilded metal alloy and features red, green, and blue glass. Due to its reflective surface and micro-relief, we anticipated that accurately digitizing this object would be particularly challenging.
2. Cross A2 features the same main theme as cross A1, but differs in both materials and size. It is made from gilded silver, white resin or bone imitation, imitation pearls, red glass, green glass, and stone. We anticipated encountering some challenges related to the glass, paste stones, and pearls.

Group B

Group B consists of two crosses, both of which date from an earlier period. The crosses differ in theme and are made from different materials. The first is entirely wooden, featuring a simple geometric form without relief decoration and covered with a painted layer. The second is a composite piece, with a carved wooden core and an elaborate metal frame. The selection criteria for the crosses in this group were based on the level of digitization difficulty. Within this group of older sanctification crosses, we chose examples representing varying degrees of complexity to highlight the unique challenges involved in their digital rendering.

1. Cross B3 is made of wood, features a painted surface, and lacks any relief decoration. We expect it to yield a high-quality 3D model because of its simple geometry and materials, as well as its low level of complexity.
2. Cross B4 features micro-relief and a metal frame adorned with wire-like decoration. It is crafted from silver, wood, and coral. We anticipated that the wire technique, coral elements, and the wooden core with carved scenes would present challenges during the digitization process. The complexity of the object necessitated detailed photography, careful lighting arrangements, and special attention to accurately rendering the upper part.

These four crosses serve as the foundation for the case study because micro-reliefs on crosses often display fine, intricate details that require high-resolution imaging and processing. Highly reflective or shiny metallic surfaces can complicate 3D reconstruction, necessitating pre-processing or alternative methods such as polarized filters and 3D scanning sprays. While these techniques are generally effective, they also present potential risks.

Our analysis explores the procedures involved in 3D modeling and rendering techniques, highlighting the challenges and opportunities they present. The primary objective is to create a digital 3D replica of an artifact using readily accessible software accompanied by straightforward guidelines for users.

The software programs we used were RealityCapture, now rebranded as RealityScan (www.realityscan.com), and Luma AI (lumalabs.ai). Both follow a similar workflow to produce high-quality results. All settings must remain consistent throughout the image capture process. Even minor changes in lighting, camera positioning, or placement of the cross can affect the final product. It is important to note that, in some cases, the same image set captured against a black background for photogrammetry also produced satisfactory results in the NeRF workflow.

Figure 2. Positioning of the cross

To ensure the creation of a high-quality 3D model, it is essential to follow specific guidelines throughout the capture process. First, the object must remain completely stationary to prevent inconsistencies or distortions in the final output. It should be placed at the center of a rotating platform (Fig. 2). Additionally, lighting conditions must remain consistent throughout the entire shooting session, as any fluctuations can adversely affect the model's accuracy and quality. We used cross-polarized lighting to capture true colors without reflections and employed a polarized filter to ensure maximum quality. The camera used during the photo shoot was a Nikon D7000, equipped with a Nikkor AF-S DX 35mm f/1.8G lens and a Hoya 52mm B-52PL-GB linear polarizer filter. The aperture was set to f/11, the exposure time to 0.62 seconds, and the ISO to 100.

A comprehensive photographic capture is essential. This process involves performing at least five full 360-degree rotations around the object, photographing it from various heights and angles. During each rotation, it is crucial to take between 50 and 70 high-resolution images, ensuring that all surfaces and details of the object are sharply focused and clearly visible. It is important to note that some artifacts have handling restrictions that must be observed.

Figure 3. Optimized camera paths for maximum image overlap

The core principles for capturing high-quality 3D models are similar in both programs. Although NeRF is more sensitive to background setup, careful and thorough image capture minimizes errors and enhances results in both methods. In our case, crosses 3 and 4 (Fig. 3) are not easily accessible, so we needed to ensure success on the first attempt.

Evaluation Protocol

Reconstructions were assessed per criterion using an anchored seven-point ordinal scale, where 1 denotes that the feature is not depicted (or is depicted incorrectly) and 7 denotes a good representation with no observable issues under the predefined viewing conditions (Table 1). Intermediate scores indicate progressively improved legibility and fidelity: 2=

faint representation, 3= not clearly depicted, 4= clear representation with several issues, 5= clear representation with few issues, 6= good representation with minor errors, 7= good representation. All criteria were scored independently by ten evaluators with expertise in conservation and 3D documentation, using the same viewing environment and predefined viewpoints. Scores are reported as structured qualitative judgments intended to support comparative interpretation.

Results

Results are presented as case-based comparative observations supported by the anchored scoring scheme (Table 1). The analysis focuses on (i) the legibility of micro-relief and fine ornamentation, (ii) perceived materiality in reflective components, and (iii) practical usability for conservation-oriented tasks, including remote inspection, documentation, and communication.

This work aims to contribute to the limited bibliographic literature on the aforementioned miniature crosses and the digital modeling of small-sized artifacts with varying reflective properties and high complexity. Comparative assessment is a central theme in research on NeRFs, as researchers seek to understand their advantages and limitations relative to established 3D reconstruction technologies, such as photogrammetry. This paper demonstrates the capability of NeRFs to handle complex lighting conditions and produce detailed visual reconstructions in scenarios where traditional photogrammetry point clouds encounter challenges and require more costly equipment. It is widely accepted that photogrammetry provides accurate geometric data and textures, while NeRFs excel at handling complex light interactions and rendering high-fidelity details. These reconstructions are often superior for models with complex and reflective surfaces. In this work, we investigate how NeRFs can address the challenges photogrammetry faces when capturing intricate micro-reliefs and reflective materials. Through these neural rendering methods, NeRF-based approaches show great promise for the future of 3D documentation of complex cultural heritage objects.

In the field of conservation, there is a need not only for precise metric data but also for highly realistic 3D visual representations of objects. We aim to analyze side-by-side visual results from both photogrammetry and NeRF to understand how each method captures details, textures, and forms. Our goal is to assess their strengths, limitations, and suitability for digitizing small, complex, and reflective objects, such as our miniature crosses.

We evaluated each cross for each criterion using an anchored seven-point ordinal scale, in which 1 denotes that the feature is not depicted (or is depicted incorrectly), and 7 denotes a good representation with no observable issues under the predefined viewing conditions (Table 1). Intermediate scores indicate progressively improved legibility and fidelity: 2= faint representation, 3= not clearly depicted, 4= clear representation with

several issues, 5= clear representation with few issues, and 6= good representation with minor errors, 7= good representation (no observable issues).

Cross A1

Figure 4. Comparison of 3D models / Cross A1

In the case of cross A1 (Fig. 4), photogrammetry produced a relatively complete model, although it struggled with the edges and the base. The color was close but not entirely accurate.

NeRF, however, was able to produce a coherent and accurate reconstruction and representation. While NeRF offers better visual results, it provides less perceived chromatic fidelity. We were unable to use the same photos taken for photogrammetry and had to resort to video capture instead (the Samsung S20+ camera was used, recording in 8K (7680×4320) and 24 frames per second). This change negatively affected the color quality of our model.

Evaluation System of 3D models

Not Depicted	Faint Representation	Not Clearly Depicted	Clear Representation with Several Issues	Clear Representation With Few Issues	Good Representation with Minor Errors	Good Representation
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Table 1 - Evaluation System of 3D models

Evaluation of 3D models / Cross A1

Object Characteristics	Photogrammetry	NeRF
Materials		
Gold	4	6
Green Glass Mass	4	6
Red GLass Masss	4	6
Blue glass Mass	4	6
Techniques		
Decorative Ends Cast	3	6
Relief Representation	7	6
Incised Script	7	5
Rosettes	7	3
Perforated Decoration	5	5
Smooth Surface	2	6
Defects-Imperfections		
Mat surface	3	6
Micro-relief	3	5
Base	3	5
Color Representation	4	6
Perforated Decoration	3	6
Measurements	3	4
Depths Representation	3	7
Lighting Representation	3	7

Table 2 - Evaluation of 3D model - Cross A1

For Cross A1, NeRFs provided higher perceived fidelity in view-dependent appearance, particularly in specular highlights and reflective transitions, whereas photogrammetry offered more stable geometric readability of edges and relief boundaries under the given capture conditions (Table 2). Both techniques enabled the identification of surface wear, micro-scratches, corrosion, and toolmarks. The geometry of the glass masses and the definition of several edge features were better perceived in the NeRF rendering. The novel-view rendering was acceptable; however, the exported model was not.

Cross A2

Figure 5. Side-by-side comparison of all three techniques used on Cross A2

In the case of Cross A2 (Fig. 5), photogrammetry produced a generally good reconstruction, although many semiprecious stones and small details were not accurately represented. NeRF produced a complete model, but some of the finer elements, especially at the antenna-like terminals, appeared distorted or altered. Visually, both models provided a plausible representation of the original object. The NeRF model showed higher perceived chromatic fidelity than the photogrammetric model.

Evaluation of 3D models / Cross A2

Object Characteristics	Photogrammetry	NeRF
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Materials		
Silver	5	6
Gold	4	5
Green Glass Mass	4	6
Red GLass Masss	4	6
Pearls	4	6
Techniques		
White Paste Stone	6	5
Pearl	7	6
Decorative Ends	5	6
Cast	7	6
Relief Representation	7	6
Incised Script	7	5
Rosettes	7	4
Perforated decoration	5	5
Smooth surface	5	5
Defects-Imperfections		
Mat Surface	6	6
Micro-Relief	6	4
Base	5	5
Color Representation	4	5
Perforated Decoration	5	6
Measurements	6	3
Depths Representation	4	7
Lighting Representation	4	7

Table 3 - Evaluation of 3D model - Cross A2

NeRF showed higher perceived fidelity than photogrammetry in detecting defects, imperfections, and materials, but did not perform as well in the representation of techniques (Table 3). For Cross A2, both techniques enabled the identification of surface wear, micro-scratches, deformation, corrosion, and toolmarks. The geometry of the glass masses, the paste, the beads, the edges, and the depth were better perceived with NeRF. The model produced in the novel view was acceptable. When we attempted to export the

model, the result was not acceptable, and several visible problems appeared. The photogrammetric model was better, but it was still not sufficiently good.

Cross B3

For Cross B3 (Fig. 6), the results of the two methods were broadly similar. However, NeRF appeared to provide a stronger visual rendering, with color, shading, and most visible details closely resembling the original object.

Figure 6. Side-by-side comparison of all three techniques used on Cross B3

The evaluation was similar across nearly all criteria, except for smooth-surface rendering, where NeRF showed higher perceived fidelity than photogrammetry (Table 4). Both techniques enabled the identification of surface wear, micro-scratches, deformation, corrosion, and toolmarks. The novel-view rendering was acceptable, and the exported model did not present significant problems, likely because of the object's low geometric complexity. Overall, the model did not exhibit many visible issues.

Evaluation of 3D models / Cross B3		
Object Characteristics	Photogrammetry	NeRF
Materials		

Wood	7	7
Techniques		
Painted Surface	6	7
Decorative Ends	7	7
Smooth Surface	5	7
Defects-Imperfections		
Wood Infestation	7	7
Wood Degradation	6	6
Mat surface	7	6
Color Representation	6	7
Measurements	7	7
Depths		
Representation	7	7
Lighting		
Representation	7	7
Table 4 - Evaluation of 3D model -Cross B3		

Cross B4

Figure 7. Side-by-side comparison of all three techniques used on Cross B4

In the case of Cross B4 (Fig. 7), both photogrammetry and NeRF produced complete models. However, the base of the NeRF model appeared overly dark. The semiprecious stones were represented less coherently in the photogrammetric model but more coherently in the NeRF rendering. Overall, both reconstructions were visually plausible and broadly resembled the original object.

Evaluation of 3D models / Cross B4		
Object Characteristics	Photogrammetry	NeRF
Materials		
Wood	5	4
Silver	5	6
Coral	4	6
Techniques		
Decorative Ends	5	6
Relief Representation	7	6
Perforated Decoration	6	5
Carved Representation	6	4

Wired Technique	6	5
Domes	4	5
Defects-Imperfections		
Oxidized	6	6
Wood Degradation	6	5
Past Conservation	6	7
Mat Surface	6	7
Micro-Relief	6	4

Table 5 - Evaluation of 3D model - Cross B4

NeRF captured the surface and reflective qualities more effectively overall. However, the technical rendering results were mixed. Both NeRF and photogrammetry techniques produced good outcomes, as demonstrated in Table 5. The main difference lay in material representation: NeRF did not capture the wood well, while photogrammetry failed to capture the coral accurately. Overall, NeRF provided a better representation of the structural details (Table 5). For Cross B4 the results of both techniques helped us identify surface wear, micro-scratches, deformation, corrosion, and toolmarks. The geometry of the corals, the small towers, and the wire technique was better perceived with NeRF. Although the novel-view rendering was acceptable, the exported model was not. Both techniques produced models with several visible problems.

Across the tested cases, NeRF more consistently preserved view-dependent appearance cues on reflective components, while photogrammetry provided more stable geometry/texture legibility under the same capture constraints. Chromatic outcomes are discussed qualitatively (perceived fidelity) rather than as calibrated accuracy. Several observations were consistent with expected differences in representational realism between the two methods under reflective capture conditions. The ultimate goal is to provide accessible software solutions that enable object replication without the need for high-end hardware. However, current technology has not yet reached a point where state-of-the-art 3D modeling techniques can deliver both detailed graphics and precise model accuracy simultaneously. NeRFs are emerging as one of the most promising approaches for the documentation of visually complex cultural heritage objects. We can clearly observe surface wear. Micro-scratches are not always easy to detect; however, they can be identified in certain cases. Small deformations cannot be easily observed, whereas more pronounced ones may be visible, although depth perception and an appropriate viewing angle are usually required. Corrosion-like features can sometimes be observed. These materials typically exhibit surface oxidation rather than rust. As for toolmarks, they can generally be detected in most cases, where present.

Discussion

This study compares close-range photogrammetry and NeRFs as two practically accessible routes for producing 3D digital surrogates of blessing and sanctification

crosses characterized by micro- to low-relief carving and mixed, often reflective materials. Because the focus is on use-oriented interpretability (surface legibility, perceived materiality, and communication-ready visualization), the following interpretation emphasizes comparative strengths and failure modes rather than benchmark-grade performance claims.

Photogrammetry remains the most widely adopted technique in cultural heritage documentation due to its cost-effectiveness and its capacity to deliver high-resolution texture maps. Within our capture constraints, improvements were primarily observed in perceived texture realism and the readability of fine engraved details, whereas geometric reliability remained sensitive to acquisition conditions. It is established that hybrid workflows (active 3D scanning for geometry combined with photogrammetry for texture) can produce high-fidelity results; however, such scanning systems are frequently inaccessible to many practitioners due to cost, portability, and required expertise. Moreover, while many scanners provide dense, metrically robust meshes, color capture and texture richness may be limited relative to dedicated photographic acquisition, depending on sensor class and workflow.

The dominant limitation of photogrammetry in this object class is its susceptibility to environmental and technical variability (illumination stability, camera settings, depth of field, and object repositioning). These sensitivities become critical for reflective or glossy surfaces, where view-dependent specular highlights violate the assumption of photometric consistency across images, complicating feature matching, depth inference, and image alignment. In practice, this can manifest as local mis-registrations, surface noise, incomplete reconstruction, or texture artifacts precisely in the areas of greatest interpretive value (polished metal, gilding, and gem settings). Accordingly, the operational objective is not simply “more images,” but capture strategies that reduce uncontrolled appearance variation (e.g., consistent lighting geometry and careful management of reflections), thereby improving the stability of reconstruction outputs.

NeRF-based rendering, by contrast, models appearance as a function of viewpoint and can therefore better accommodate view-dependent effects in principle—an especially relevant property for reflective metallic heritage items. Although NeRF methods are increasingly visible across computer vision, their systematic adoption in cultural heritage practice remains comparatively limited, and most published demonstrations emphasize architectural or large-scale scenes rather than miniature, highly reflective objects. Within this scope, our observations suggest that radiance-field representations can improve the perceived continuity of specular behavior and the plausibility of reflective transitions, which can enhance the visual legibility of micro-relief in dissemination and remote viewing contexts. At the same time, these benefits should be understood as improvements in perceived representational fidelity (material appearance cues) rather than direct evidence of metric superiority in geometry.

The present comparison was designed to test method performance across realistic documentation scenarios and to identify recurring challenges in digitizing micro-ornamented crosses with mixed materials. Framed conservatively, the practical trade-off is as follows: photogrammetry offers a familiar, interoperable path to textured meshes that support many downstream heritage workflows, whereas NeRF-type representations may better preserve view-dependent appearance cues that are central to “reading” reflective surfaces. This trade-off is not merely technical, it aligns with distinct user needs,

including conservation-oriented inspection (surface changes, abrasion patterns, loss of sheen), scholarly study (micro-relief interpretability), and museum communication (credible presentation of brilliance and finish).

Beyond geometric correspondence, cultural heritage digitization must also address how artifacts are visually and culturally perceived. For many devotional and precious-metal objects, “truthfulness” in presentation is strongly mediated by controlled lighting, specular response, and chromatic atmosphere—features that shape historical intent and audience reception. Accordingly, removing an object from its functional lighting and display context (e.g., presenting a jewelled metallic cross without adequate illumination) can suppress precisely the perceptual cues through which the artifact’s craftsmanship and symbolic presence are communicated. In this sense, geometry alone is insufficient: the artifact’s value is also carried by its materiality, color appearance, and the way it orchestrates light, all of which contribute to interpretive coherence for experts and the public. Therefore, a documentation strategy should be judged not only by mesh precision, but also by its capacity to preserve the artifact’s perceptual intelligibility and communicative intent within the constraints of the intended use.

Limitations

The study is intentionally pilot in scale (four objects) and relies on structured qualitative scoring rather than instrument-based metrology. No colorimetric calibration was performed; therefore, chromatic outcomes are discussed in terms of perceived fidelity rather than accuracy. In addition, the NeRF workflow is partly constrained by proprietary processing and export options, limiting transparency of model configuration. Consequently, findings should be interpreted as practice-oriented comparative insights for reflective miniature objects rather than benchmark claims.

Conclusions and conservation implications

This study examined two accessible 3D digitization paradigms—close-range photogrammetry and NeRFs—for blessing and sanctification crosses characterized by micro- to low-relief carving, mixed materials, and locally reflective surfaces. Under realistic capture constraints and a structured qualitative evaluation, the comparison indicates a consistent methodological trade-off: photogrammetry remains a reliable baseline for producing interoperable textured meshes suited to conventional documentation pipelines, whereas radiance-field representations tend to preserve view-dependent appearance cues that are critical for the perceptual reading of reflective metalwork and fine surface relief. Importantly, these findings should be interpreted as practice-oriented comparative insights rather than benchmark performance claims.

From a conservation standpoint, the results reinforce that “fitness for purpose” should guide method selection. When preventive conservation priorities include the monitoring of subtle surface change—such as abrasion patterns, loss of polish, localized dulling, micro-scratches, and the visual signatures of handling—representations that preserve reflectance behavior can improve interpretability during remote inspection and inter-institutional consultation. In such contexts, NeRF-type models may offer added value by maintaining coherent specular responses across viewpoints, enabling conservators to better apprehend changes in finish and the continuity of micro-relief under virtual relighting/viewing. Conversely, where conservation workflows require stable geometry for

measurement, alignment to reference coordinate systems, integration with condition maps, or long-term comparability via repeatable mesh-based outputs, photogrammetry (and, where feasible, hybrid scanning–photogrammetry workflows) remains the more robust option.

The study further highlights that reflective miniature objects expose a core limitation of standard photogrammetric assumptions: uncontrolled view-dependent highlights and illumination variability can propagate into alignment instability, local surface noise, and texture artifacts exactly where conservation interest is concentrated (edges, engraving, polished metal, and gem settings). Therefore, even in low-cost deployments, preventive conservation programs should explicitly plan capture protocols that minimize uncontrolled appearance variation—through consistent illumination geometry, stable camera settings, careful object positioning, and, where possible, reflection management—so that repeated campaigns can support meaningful visual comparison over time. In parallel, radiance-field approaches should be treated as complementary tools that can enhance communicative fidelity and interpretability for reflective materials, while acknowledging current constraints related to workflow transparency, exportability, and standardization.

More broadly, the work argues for an expanded conservation lens in 3D documentation: beyond geometric correspondence, digital surrogates should be evaluated for their capacity to preserve the perceptual intelligibility of an artifact’s materiality. For devotional metalwork, brilliance, sheen, and localized reflectance transitions are not incidental, they are part of the object’s intended visual effect and, in many cases, part of the evidence base used to interpret workmanship, wear, and past interventions. Accordingly, documentation strategies that combine conventional mesh outputs (for interoperability and measurement) with radiance-field visualizations (for view-dependent appearance) offer a pragmatic route toward both scientific utility and museum-facing communication. Future work should strengthen the evidential base through (i) repeat-capture campaigns to evaluate sensitivity to time-dependent surface change, (ii) explicit documentation of radiance-field configuration and export pathways, and (iii) calibration steps (geometric and colorimetric) where claims of accuracy are required. Nonetheless, within the scope of this pilot study, the comparative findings provide actionable guidance for selecting and combining 3D digitization methods for reflective, micro-ornamented heritage objects in preventive conservation and interpretation workflows.

Future directions: radiance-field digitisation with 3D Gaussian Splatting

Recent advances in radiance-field representations—most notably 3D Gaussian Splatting—suggest a practical next step beyond classical NeRF pipelines for the digitisation of reflective, micro-ornamented heritage objects. Unlike many NeRF implementations that rely on expensive volumetric sampling and comparatively slow optimization/rendering, 3DGS represents scenes as an adaptive set of anisotropic 3D Gaussians and employs a visibility-aware splatting renderer, enabling substantially faster optimization and real-time novel-view synthesis while retaining high visual fidelity (Kerbl et al. 2023).

For cultural heritage, these properties are not merely computational conveniences: they unlock new documentation and conservation-facing workflows that are difficult to support with slower NeRF pipelines. First, real-time rendering makes 3DGS inherently well-suited to interactive inspection (desktop/VR/AR), where conservators and curators can examine micro-relief and reflective transitions dynamically, rather than relying on pre-rendered viewpoints. Second, faster training and iteration reduces the barrier to capture–reconstruction cycles, enabling on-site “rapid feedback” acquisition: capture gaps (missing angles, problematic specular zones, insufficient depth of field) can be detected early and corrected during the same session—an operational advantage for fragile objects with limited handling time (Kerbl et al. 2023).

Third, emerging heritage-focused adaptations of 3DGS indicate that the method is being actively tailored to artifact-centric constraints (background interference, alignment fragility, and capture conditions that differ from scene-scale datasets; Lee, et al. 2025). For small reflective objects, two methodological directions are particularly relevant: (i) improving robustness to imperfect capture alignment and non-ideal acquisition environments, and (ii) isolating the artifact from the surrounding scene so that reconstruction capacity is concentrated on the object rather than background geometry and clutter (Lee et al. 2025).

Within a preventive conservation framework, 3DGS enables several concrete research directions that extend the present study. (1) Repeat-capture monitoring with interactive change screening: repeated 3DGS reconstructions acquired under controlled lighting geometry can support comparative visual inspection of sheen loss, abrasion patterns, and localized reflective discontinuities—features that are often diagnostically meaningful for handling damage and surface alteration. (2) Multimodal radiance-field fusion: integrating close-range photogrammetry’s high-resolution texture priors and/or structured-light geometry constraints with 3DGS optimization could yield hybrid representations that preserve both metric stability (for measurement and mapping) and view-dependent appearance (for material legibility). (3) Museum-facing dissemination pipelines: real-time 3DGS models can be deployed in interactive exhibits and web-based viewers with far lower latency than conventional NeRF renderers, improving accessibility while maintaining the perceptual coherence of reflective devotional objects (Jamil and Brennan, 2025; Mirocha, 2025).

Finally, adopting 3DGS as a research direction should be accompanied by explicit standardization efforts to meet conservation requirements. Future studies should report (i) acquisition control parameters (illumination geometry, polarization strategy where relevant, depth-of-field management), (ii) reconstruction transparency (software versions, optimization schedules, density-control settings), and (iii) evaluation design that separates perceptual fidelity from metrological claims. Positioning 3DGS as a high-throughput, real-time radiance-field representation—rather than merely a faster “NeRF replacement”—will strengthen its scientific value for reflective heritage documentation by linking its computational advantages directly to conservation decision-making, remote expert consultation, and repeatable monitoring workflows.

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